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E-Learning Educational Atmosphere and Technology Integration as Predictors of Students' Engagement: The Case of Agribusiness Program

¹Ronald E. Almagro, ²Hazel C. Montepio & ³Ma. Theresa O. Tuquib

Abstract

This study aimed to determine whether the e-learning educational atmosphere and technology integration significantly influence the students' engagement. The study employed a descriptive-correlational research design with 127 fourth-year college students from Davao del Norte, Philippines selected through universal sampling. The study used three adapted questionnaires to gather data, and statistical tools such as mean, Pearson r, standard deviation, and regression analysis were utilized. The e-learning educational atmosphere on students in terms of programme effectiveness, teaching quality, ethics and professionalism, learner support, safety and convenience, and awareness of the rules is much observed. Students' engagement, perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and attitude toward integrating are much evident. Students' engagement in terms of affective, behavioral, and cognitive are much manifested. The findings also revealed that the e-learning educational atmosphere has a significant relationship and influence on students' engagement. On the other hand, technology integration has a significant relationship and influence on students' engagement. The study highlights the importance of creating a safe and convenient e-learning environment and promoting the use of technology in enhancing students' engagement. The study's limitations include the sample size and the context-specific findings. The results imply the need for instructors, school administrators, and CHED officials to collaborate and establish programs that promote students' engagement through e-learning and technology integration.

Keywords: *E-learning educational atmosphere, Technology Integration, Students' engagement*

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1. Introduction

Student engagement played a pivotal role in cultivating students' levels of attention, curiosity, interest, optimism, and passion. It served as a clear indicator of their commitment and active participation in the educational journey (Groccia, 2018). In recent times, the declining engagement levels of students have emerged as a growing concern that has left its mark on the realm of education. To facilitate meaningful and inclusive learning experiences, a strong partnership between educators and students is imperative, and this can only materialize when students are fully engaged (Nalipay et al., 2020). Nonetheless, numerous college students encountered hurdles when it came to engaging with courses related to agriculture, primarily due to the absence of an authentic learning environment. Consequently, many students grappled with comprehending and recognizing the real-world relevance of global agricultural subjects (Kiezel et al., 2020). Furthermore, disinterest in agricultural topics could also be attributed to unfavorable perceptions of the course itself and doubts regarding the effectiveness and practicality of instructors' teaching methodologies within the learning environment (Irani-Kermani et al., 2021). Sustaining student engagement in a course has posed a recurring challenge, irrespective of the learning mode, whether it be remote, face-to-face, or a hybrid model (Sutton & Jorge, 2020). Therefore, it remains imperative to devise effective strategies aimed at bolstering student engagement and nurturing a constructive and conducive learning atmosphere that kindles students' enthusiasm for the educational process.

The insufficient enthusiasm among college students in the Philippines regarding agricultural subjects has emerged as a pressing concern hindering the progress of the country's agricultural sector. Recent research conducted by David et al. in 2022 highlighted that this issue has led to a notable disparity in students' motivation to engage in the growth of the agricultural industry, either through establishing their own agricultural enterprises or continuing their family's agricultural businesses. This waning interest has prompted a shift away from agricultural courses and professions towards the industrial and service sectors, exacerbating the country's agricultural underdevelopment. Considering the vital role agriculture plays in the Philippine economy and people's livelihoods, addressing this concern became an urgent matter demanding attention from policymakers, educators, and various stakeholders. Consequently, it became imperative to identify the root causes contributing to students' disinterest in agricultural topics and devise effective strategies to reverse this trend. Potential actions may have included elevating the quality of agricultural education, expanding outreach initiatives to stimulate youth interest in agriculture, and providing incentives and support for students aspiring to pursue agricultural careers.

In the local college of Sto. Tomas, Davao del Norte, a common observation was the varying levels of student engagement in agriculture-related courses. Surprisingly, there seemed to be a gap in published research addressing this issue. Nevertheless, further investigation conducted in Davao City, encompassing three tertiary institutions, unveiled a noteworthy trend. It became evident that negative sentiments and personal biases regarding agri-business had a discouraging effect on the involvement of some students in agriculture-related subjects. Furthermore, it was observed that these students harbored diverse motivations for pursuing courses in agriculture, resulting in a range

of challenges related to their engagement with the subject matter. For instance, a subset of these students did not envision themselves as future farmers. Instead, they aspired to join the service sector, be it in government, industry, or marketing, as they did not perceive agriculture and farming as viable career options (Manigo, 2021).

Additionally, previous research has demonstrated the significant influence of e-learning educational settings on student engagement (Xu et al., 2020). However, these investigations did not specifically delve into the realm of student engagement within agriculture courses, especially at the higher education level. Although certain studies have focused on engagement among secondary education students, there remains a notable gap in the literature when it comes to exploring this subject among tertiary-level students. Consequently, the primary objective of this study was to address this gap by investigating the engagement levels of students pursuing agriculture courses at the tertiary level. This research delved into the intricate interplay between e-learning educational environments, technology integration, and student engagement within the context of agriculture courses. Notably, there was a notable absence of similar research conducted within the specific region where this study took place, underscoring the novelty and importance of this research initiative in advancing our understanding of agricultural education. Through an examination of the factors influencing student engagement in tertiary-level agricultural courses, this study offered invaluable insights into the design of effective e-learning environments tailored to the field of agricultural education.

This study had the objective of delving into and enhancing the participation of students in agricultural courses, with a specific emphasis on harnessing the e-learning environment and integrating technology. This research was motivated by the demands brought about by the "new normal" circumstances, where virtual learning and remote education have become the standard. By offering fresh perspectives into how the e-learning environment, technology integration, and student engagement are interconnected in agricultural courses, this study aimed to make a valuable contribution to the evolution of agricultural education curricula and policies. The outcomes of this research had the potential to guide the creation of inventive teaching methodologies and approaches tailored to augment student involvement in agricultural courses. This study could be particularly advantageous to educators and other professionals in the field of education, offering insights to address the distinct requirements and challenges encountered in 21st-century agricultural education. In essence, this research marked a crucial stride towards enhancing the caliber and efficiency of agricultural education in response to the unparalleled challenges introduced by the "new normal" situation.

The researcher found the urgency to conduct this study to fill the gap in the literature covering the concern of e-learning educational atmosphere, technology integration, and students' Engagement in agriculture courses, especially in the local context. In addition, to the best of the researcher's knowledge, the conduct of the study was urgent since the modality and the delivery of teaching agriculture courses in the present times were still constrained within the bounds of blended virtual and face-to-face interaction. Additionally, the researcher observed that the local

state college where this study was conducted was still utilizing the blended learning environment such as virtual and face-to-face learning modalities.

Moreover, the researcher disseminated the results of the study by attending research forums in both the public and private sectors of educational institutions. Additionally, copies of the study were given to concerned beneficiaries, such as students with agriculture-related courses or majors, instructors, parents, and other individuals, in order to contribute an additional body of knowledge on the different aspects of the relationship between e-learning educational atmosphere, technology integration, and student engagement in agriculture courses. The dissemination of research findings took place in agricultural-research conferences, agribusiness education seminars, and other educational avenues where the findings could be effectively shared.

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of the study was to determine whether the e-learning educational atmosphere and technology integration had a significant influence on the engagement of fourth-year college students in agriculture courses in the Sto. Tomas College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology during the academic year 2022-2023.

The study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of e-learning educational atmosphere of students in terms of:
 - 1.1. program effectiveness;
 - 1.2. teaching quality; and
 - 1.3. ethics and professionalism
 - 1.4. learner support
 - 1.5. safety and convenience; and
 - 1.6. awareness of the rules?
2. What is the level of technology integration in terms of:
 - 2.1 perceived ease of use;
 - 2.2 perceived usefulness; and
 - 2.3 attitude toward integrating?
2. What is the level of students' Engagement in an agriculture course in terms of:
 - 3.1 affective Engagement
 - 3.2 behavioral Engagement; and
 - 3.3 cognitive Engagement?
4. Is there a significant relationship between:
 - 4.1 e-learning educational atmosphere and student engagement in an agriculture course?
 - 4.2 technology integration and student engagement in an agriculture course?
5. Do e-learning educational atmosphere and technology integration significantly influence students' Engagement in an agriculture course?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance to determine whether learning educational atmosphere and technology integration significantly influenced students' engagement in an agriculture course:

1. There was no significant relationship between the e-learning educational atmosphere and students' engagement in an agriculture-related course.
2. There was no significant relationship between technology integration and students' engagement in an agriculture-related course.
3. E-learning educational atmosphere and technology integration did not significantly influence students' engagement in an agriculture-related course.

2. Literature review

The following are taken from different pieces of literature which are related to the study. Specifically, this presents a substantial discussion of literature that address student engagement in agriculture-related course, e-learning educational atmosphere, and technology integration.

Student Engagement

Engagement has been identified as a crucial element of effective interventions in a learning environment by researchers. Moreover, there is a connection between joint engagement and classroom conditions, as well as student characteristics. Significant correlations exist between group size, student-directed activities, and expressive communication abilities and engagement (Steinbrenner & Watson, 2015). The extent to which students think, feel, and behave engaged in school is crucial to their academic and personal success, yet student engagement levels remain low. The more involved students are with their schoolwork, the more likely they are to perform well academically and achieve higher grades (Gumban et al., 2020). Moreover, creating learning environments that take into consideration the uniqueness of each student and their relationships with one another may increase student involvement in the learning process (Gaspard & Lauermaun, 2021).

In enhancing students' engagement, utilizing blended learning with an interactive learning environment is a successful teaching strategy for capturing students' attention, according to classroom-based studies (Gil-Doménech & Berbegal-Mirabent, 2019). On the other hand, the relationships that students cultivate in their classes are likely to affect their academic progress. As expected, hierarchical mediating studies revealed that the positive association between classroom emotional climate and grades is mediated by students' engagement, adjusting for teacher characteristics, and classroom observations of both organizational and instructional environments. Effects are strong regardless of grade level or gender of students. This observation highlights the relevance of emotional classroom interactions in fostering academic accomplishment and increasing student engagement (Gutman & Schoon, 2018).

E-learning educational atmosphere

Universities evaluate their academic learning environment in order to enhance student learning. Students' experiences in an e-learning environment vary from those in a traditional classroom (Mousavi et al., 2020). Even though e-learning is being used in developed nations where its readiness and efficacy have been studied, they believe that e-learning is an effective alternative to traditional lecture-based instruction. Recently, the majority of schools throughout the world have swiftly shifted from conventional face-to-face instruction to online learning. However, this change presents a difficulty for underdeveloped nations. The adoption of e-learning is hindered by a lack of adequate technology infrastructure, limited financial resources, limited evaluation methods, and instructors lacking the pedagogical abilities necessary to present information electronically (Mubeen, et al., 2020). Furthermore, traditional education must be reformed since it does not engage students in active learning. As a result, in the twenty-first century, the advancement of internet technology in the educational environment has become a primary objective for each student. Therefore, a web-based or e-learning environment is one of the learning environments that may be used to satisfy the demands of the teaching and learning process (Hamzah et al., 2017).

Technology Integration

Technology is an important component of our daily lives. In reality, students in our public schools are digital natives who are habituated to being constantly linked to the Internet and their gadgets (Harrell & Bynum, 2018). Given the significance of technology in our lives, schools must now incorporate it into classroom instruction and prepare students for 21st-century skills and opportunities (Tan et al., 2021). In recent years, technology integration has become a key tool in virtually every workplace and has offered educators a vital resource to help teaching and learning (Mac Callum et al., 2014). However, despite the fact that schools may have access to numerous advanced technologies, there are a number of external and internal elements that influence the application of technology in classrooms. Technology integration is essential for preparing students for higher education (Harrell & Bynum, 2018).

In education, a significant study has been conducted on technology-enhanced mathematics education and the perceived potential of digital technologies to enhance the learning process (Bray & Tangney, 2017). In relation, in some conditions, technology integration including programming, can increase student enthusiasm to learn a subject and enhance student performance. To acquire a better understanding of the possibilities of integrating technology, it is necessary to examine the complete collective learning process, including the duties of the teacher and the cooperation between students as part of these responsibilities (Forsström & Kaufmann, 2018).

2.1 Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on Flavell's (1987) metacognitive theory, which claimed that as students engaged with adaptive course content, the system gathered and stored their data, which may have included information about their degree of confidence, accuracy, knowledge, and other factors. The direct and indirect advantages of e-learning were emphasized as having played a critical role in inspiring students to study and increase their engagement with a certain subject or course (Shih, C et al., 2021). An e-learning educational environment had an influence on student

engagement on the subject or course by breaking down time and place barriers, allowing students to connect and cooperate without needing to be in the same area at the same time. This learning environment employed a technique in which the internet served as the primary medium for rapidly providing academic programs for teaching and learning (Aboobaker & Muneer, 2021). Moreover, Muhametjanova and Akmatbekova (2019) emphasized that, in addition to the course format, an e-learning environment's flexibility had been identified as a factor influencing student engagement in a course through their assessments of the significance of certain progress that reflected their mastery objectives and aspirations to become knowledgeable in a specific field or course.

On the other hand, this study was also guided by the ideas that given the importance of technology, technological integration had become a fundamental component of higher education, impacting many aspects of learners' experiences and improving student engagement through behavioral, emotional, and cognitive student involvement in a course or subject matter (Bond M. 2020). In relation, technology integration was an important tool for increasing student engagement in a course or material by providing teachers with a great resource for effective instruction such as facilitating interactive activities, contextualized lessons, and meaningful assessments (Loannou, et al., 2019). Furthermore, technology integration increased student engagement in a learning setting because teachers used various instructional platforms that helped to improve student engagement in a classroom setting by learning effectively through interactive communication, peer collaboration, and meaningful discussion (Bond & Bedenlier, 2019).

Furthermore, Mousavi et al. (2020) emphasized that Programme Effectiveness, Teaching Quality, Ethics and Professionalism, Learner Support, Safety and Convenience, and Awareness of the Rules, were the six (6) components of an e-learning educational atmosphere. Additionally, Al-Abdullatif and Gameil (2021) identified that Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Usefulness, Attitude toward Integrating, and Academic Performance were the four (4) components of technology integration. Moreover, Hart et al. (2011) further identified that Affective Engagement, Behavioral Engagement, and Cognitive Engagement were the three (3) dimensions that comprised student engagement.

2.3 Conceptual Framework

The study's conceptual paradigm was shown in Figure 1. It summarized the variables of the study which were e-learning educational atmosphere, technology integration, and student engagement. The first independent variable was the e-learning educational atmosphere. The indicators were Programme Effectiveness, Teaching Quality, Ethics and Professionalism, Learner Support, Safety and Convenience, and Awareness of the Rules. The second independent variable was technology integration to which the measures were classified into Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Usefulness, Attitude toward Integrating, and Academic Performance. Moreover, the dependent variable was student engagement in agriculture-related course as measured in terms of Affective Engagement, Behavioral Engagement, and Cognitive Engagement.

Figure 1. The Conceptual Paradigm of the Study

2.4 Significance of the Study

The success of this study was beneficial to the following groups of people. In particular, this was useful to the following:

Students. This research helped students recognize the importance of an e-learning educational atmosphere and technology integration in enhancing their engagement in an agriculture-related course. This inspired students to use innovative ways to help them effectively engage and better learn more in agricultural courses. Furthermore, the findings of this research provided students with a greater awareness of the value of their learning through the connections of e-learning educational atmosphere, technology integration, and their engagement as learners.

Teachers. This study was beneficial for them in developing creative and better teaching strategies that inspired students to enhance their engagement in agricultural courses, and they used the findings to meet the demands and problems of 21st-century education. Furthermore, the findings of this research provided teachers with an extra body of information in teaching agriculture-related courses, which was a significant aspect in the students' learning process. This research helped to successfully improve students' engagement when it came to teaching agriculture-related courses and topics.

School Administrators. They created teaching enhancement programs and seminars to address the need for students to acquire better engagement and to educate teachers to be aware of

the potential advantages of an e-learning educational atmosphere and technology integration in the learning process. They provided such assistance to teachers' various needs to improve classroom management and delivery of instructions. Furthermore, how administrators supported students and teachers professionally had an influence on their performance. This research was used as a guide in administering the teachers' and students' teaching and learning processes.

Ched Officials. This research offered them sufficient and additional body of knowledge to be successful in creating and executing effective programs as they conducted workshops, seminars, and webinars to improve students' engagement to achieve a high-quality teaching-learning environment. Moreover, the findings of this study were useful resources for creating educational initiatives that could be beneficial for both educators and learners within the institution.

Future Researchers. As part of their study's associated literature, the results of this study functioned as an excellent basis for future studies. This study added to the body of knowledge in the areas of e-learning educational atmosphere, technology integration, and student engagement in agriculture-related courses.

3. Methodology

This section covered the study's numerous methodologies, which included the research design, respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedures, statistical treatment of data, and ethical considerations.

3.1 Research Design

A quantitative non-experimental applying descriptive and correlational approach design was used in this study. A quantitative research method included the collection and analysis of numerical data. It was useful for identifying patterns and averages, making forecasts, examining causal linkages, and generalizing conclusions to larger groups (Bhandari, 2020). Additionally, quantitative research was a technique for gaining knowledge about a specific group of individuals, referred to as a sample population. It used scientific inquiry to evaluate issues about a sample population via the use of observed or measured data (Creswell, 2017). Moreover, non-experimental designs were research methods that were used to explore social phenomena without manipulating the environment under which the individuals lived. Additionally, there was no random assignment of respondents to various groups (Frey et al., 2018).

The descriptive approach aimed to investigate language learning and instruction in its natural environments, without any intervention or modification of factors. The descriptive approach's objective was to characterize a phenomenon and its features. Additionally, it was more interested in what occurred than in how or why something existed (Nassaji, 2015). Furthermore, the correlational approach sought to establish correlations between two or more variables. It described seeing whether a rise or decrease in one variable was accompanied by an increase or decrease in another (Tan, 2014). Similarly, Frey (2018) defined the correlational approach as concerned with the examination of the links between two or more domains.

The above-mentioned design was used by the researcher to address the main interests and objectives of the study. Specifically, the descriptive approach was used by the researcher to explore, determine, and describe students' e-learning educational atmosphere, technology integration, and Engagement in an agriculture course as variables of the study. Moreover, a correlational approach was used to test and determine the existing relationships of e-learning educational atmosphere, technology integration, and Engagement in an agriculture-related course of students.

3.2 Research Subject

The respondents of this research were tertiary-level students enrolled in an agriculture-related course for the school year 2022-2023. The respondents' total population size of this study, collectively comprised 127 students coming from one (1) Department in one of the Local Colleges in Davao del Norte. Furthermore, this study utilized a universal sampling technique to achieve the optimum complexity for any class of signal. Similarly, Richard & Margarete 1978 stated that when a sample was chosen, universal sampling meant that not every member of the population had the same chance of being chosen, and that each person's chance of selection was unknown.

3.3 Research Instruments

Three research instruments were adapted for use in the study. They were modified to align with the study's overall objectives. A panel of experts validated the three research instruments. Additionally, a group of tertiary-level students from Davao del Norte local colleges, who were not part of the research, pilot-tested the questionnaires. This ensured that the questionnaires had high reliability for use in accomplishing the study's overall objective.

E-learning Educational Atmosphere Measure (EEAM). This instrument contains a 32-item survey questionnaire comprising the five (5) components of an e-learning educational atmosphere as Programme Effectiveness (6 items), Teaching Quality (6 items), Ethics and Professionalism (6 items), Learner Support (5 items), Safety and Convenience (5 items), and Awareness of the Rules (4 items). For reliability, the following are the Cronbach alpha values of each variable of the questionnaire: Programme Effectiveness (PE)= 0.744, Teaching Quality (TQ)= 0.704, Ethics and Professionalism (EP)= 0.752, Learner Support (LS)= 0.809, Safety and Convenience (SC)= 0.894, and Awareness of Rules (AW)= 0.872 which collectively had 0.796 reliability. This questionnaire was anchored on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from: 5-Strongly agree, 4-Agree, 3-Moderately Agree, 2-Disagree, and 1-Strongly Disagree.

The following parameter limits, with their corresponding descriptions, were applied to the level of students' e-learning educational atmosphere.

Parameter Limits	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	This indicates that an e-learning educational atmosphere is observed at all times.
3.40 – 4.19	High	This indicates that an e-learning educational atmosphere is observed most of the time.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	This indicates that an e-learning educational atmosphere is observed sometimes.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	This indicates that an e-learning educational atmosphere is observed rarely.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This indicates that an e-learning educational atmosphere is not observed.

Digital Technology Integration Questionnaire (DTIQ). This instrument contains a 15-item survey questionnaire that comprises the four (4) components of technology integration Perceived Ease of Use (5 items), Perceived Usefulness (5 items), and Attitude toward Integrating (4 items). For reliability, the following are the Cronbach alpha values of each variable of the questionnaire: Perceived Ease of Use (PEU)= 0.903, Perceived Usefulness (PU)= 0.866, and Attitude toward Integrating (AI)= 0.849 which collectively had 0.872 reliability. This questionnaire was anchored on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from: 5-*Strongly agree*, 4-*Agree*, 3-*Moderately Agree*, 2-*Disagree*, and 1-*Strongly Disagree*.

The following parameter limits, with their corresponding descriptions, were applied to the level of technology integration.

Parameter Limits	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	This indicates that technology integration is evident at all times.
3.40 – 4.19	High	This indicates that technology integration is evident most of the time.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	This indicates that technology integration is evident sometimes.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	This indicates that technology integration evident rarely.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This indicates that technology integration is not evident.

Student Engagement in Schools Questionnaire (SESQ). This instrument contains a 21-item survey questionnaire that comprises the three (3) components of student engagement as Affective Engagement (6 items), Behavioral Engagement (6 items), and Cognitive Engagement (9 items). For reliability, the following are the Cronbach alpha values of each variable of the questionnaire: Affective Engagement (AE)= 0.804, Behavioral Engagement (BE)= 0.822, and Cognitive Engagement (CE)= 0.849 which collectively had 0.842 reliability. This questionnaire was

anchored on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from: 5-*Strongly agree*, 4-*Agree*, 3-*Moderately Agree*, 2-*Disagree*, and 1-*Strongly Disagree*.

The following parameter limits, with their corresponding descriptions, were applied to the level of students' Engagement.

Parameter Limits	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	This means that students' Engagement is manifested all the time.
3.40 – 4.19	High	This means that students' Engagement is manifested most of the time.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	This means that students' Engagement is manifested sometimes.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	This means that students' Engagement is manifested rarely.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This means that students' Engagement is not manifested.

3.4 Data Gathering Procedure

The necessary data was gathered in a systematic procedure, which involved the following.

Permission to conduct the study was sought. The researcher sought approval to conduct the research project. Primarily, the researcher got a letter of recommendation from the President of Santo Tomas College of Agriculture, Sciences, And Technology (STCAST). After acceptance, the researcher submitted a copy of the recommendation to the respective Department Head of the following 1 (1) Degree Program such as Bachelor of Science in Agriculture and Business (BSAB).

General orientation and seeking of consent from research respondents. The conduct of the study was guided by ethical principles (respect for individuals, beneficence, and justice), most notably regarding data privacy and its protections. Before data collection, the researcher created informed consent/informed assent forms and obtained them from respondents via email message. All forms were sent and signed electronically by those research respondents via email message as evidence of voluntary participation in the entire study. In addition, the researcher also led a short 30-minute virtual presentation to the respondents about his research. In line with this, those respondents who confirmed their voluntary participation in the study were given a specific link to a google classroom created by the researcher for them to join the short virtual presentation. Specifically, this was done before conducting the study. On the other hand, those respondents who were unable to attend the orientation (considering different circumstances and even personal reasons), were still informed about the research through phone calls or messenger chat by the researcher. Additionally, a recorded video from the virtual presentation was provided to all respondents that could be accessed inside the google classroom created by the researcher intended for the research.

Administration and retrieval of the questionnaire. The research took place in December of the School Year 2022-2023. In line with conducting the research, the researcher firstly created the google forms that were used to collect answers of the respondents based on those survey questions from the questionnaires. Using Google Forms, the quantitative data for this study was gathered online. The researcher actively handled all contact and administration of questionnaires to respondents directly. All surveys were allotted within one 90-minute session commencing with the E-learning Educational Atmosphere Measure (EEAM), Digital technology Integration Questionnaire (DTIQ), and Student Engagement in Schools Questionnaire (SESQ). To safeguard the data, when answering the Google Form, the respondents were asked to complete the survey at a location and a technological device (such as laptop, cellphone, or tablet) where only they had access to those given online survey questionnaires via google forms. Specifically, this was clearly noted in their Informed Consent Form (ICF). Furthermore, the data questionnaire was returned to the researcher in a timely manner. Additionally, personal communication and administration of the questionnaire were handled by the researcher. Finally, surveys administered were obtained when the respondents' stipulated 90-minute session had expired.

Checking, collating, and processing of data. In this phase, the researcher collected, verified, and quantified the respondents' scores obtained in an excel format. After tabulation, the data was submitted for data analysis by the expert or certified statistician. Based on the data analysis, the results were interpreted by the researcher for specific findings, discussions, and conclusions. Specifically, this was done through table and graphical presentations of data. Moreover, descriptive statements were also utilized to further elaborate and clearly understand the findings in relation to those variables of the study.

3.5 Statistical Tool for Data Analysis

The findings of this study were examined and comprehended appropriately using the following statistical tools such as Mean, Standard Deviation, Pearson r, and Multiple Regression Analysis.

Mean. This method of analysis was used to measure the level of E-learning Educational Atmosphere, Technology Integration, and Student Engagement in Agriculture-Related Course. Specifically, this addressed research questions 1, 2, and 3.

Standard Deviation. A standard deviation was a statistical measure of a dataset's dispersion in relation to its mean. This method of analysis was used to measure how widely the data distributed or near to the mean the scores were. Specifically, this addressed research questions 1, 2, and 3.

Pearson r. This statistical analysis was utilized to establish the existence of a meaningful association between of E-learning Educational Atmosphere, Technology Integration, and Student

Engagement in Agriculture-Related Course. This was utilized to specifically address research question 4.

Multiple Regression Analysis. Regression analysis was a collection of statistical procedures for determining the connections among one or more dependent variables and one or more independent variables. This was used to ascertain the relationships between of E-learning Educational Atmosphere, Technology Integration, and Student Engagement in Agriculture-Related Course. Specifically, this was utilized to address research question 5.

4. Findings and Discussion

This chapter presented the results and discussions of the study. In particular, the data in tables and its corresponding descriptive interpretations were shown.

4.1 Summary on the E-learning Educational Atmosphere of Students

Table 1 presented the summary of the level of e-learning educational atmosphere of students. Based on the results, awareness of the rules obtained the highest mean score of 4.50, which was described as very high. Similarly, teaching quality and ethics and professionalism obtained a mean score of 4.43, which was also described as very high. Learner support followed closely with a mean score of 4.31. Program effectiveness also scored high with a mean score of 4.30, which was described as very high. On the other hand, safety and convenience scored the lowest with a mean score of 4.12. In addition, descriptive equivalent of much observed was assigned to program effectiveness, awareness of the rules, teaching quality, ethics and professionalism, and learner support. However, items related to safety and convenience were observed. The standard deviation of 0.66 in the overall mean indicates that the measures of variability of the e-learning educational atmosphere of students are near the mean. Therefore, this shows the homogeneity of the responses of students in this variable.

Table 1

Summary on the E-learning Educational Atmosphere of Students

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Programme Effectiveness	.67	4.30	Very High
2. Teaching Quality	.64	4.43	Very High
3. Ethics and Professionalism	.62	4.43	Very High
4. Learner Support	.67	4.31	Very High
5. Safety and Convenience	.74	4.12	High
6. Awareness of the rules	.59	4.50	Very High
Overall	.66	4.35	Very High

The study's findings shows that students' awareness of rules as part of their e-learning educational atmosphere is highly observed. This implies that students place great importance on being aware of the rules in their learning environment. Additionally, the study found that teaching quality is a critical aspect of e-learning, as instructors with high teaching quality perform well in tasks that involve electronic learning educational atmosphere. Furthermore, traditional education

must undergo reforms, as it does not involve students in active learning. As a result, the advancement of internet technology in the educational environment has become a primary objective for each student in the twenty-first century. Therefore, a web-based or e-learning environment is a learning environment that may be utilized to fulfill the demands of the teaching and learning process (Hamzah et al., 2017).

A recent study on the level of e-learning educational atmosphere of students found that those who have access to a positive e-learning environment tend to have better academic performance and higher levels of satisfaction with their online courses (González-Gómez et al., 2016). The study identified that factors such as social presence, ease of use, and usefulness of the e-learning platform all contribute to the creation of a positive e-learning environment (Alsabawy et al., 2018). However, it is crucial to note that the success of e-learning also depends on the level of interaction between the instructor and the students (Park & Choi, 2009). These findings underscore the importance of establishing a positive e-learning atmosphere that promotes student engagement, satisfaction, and academic success through a combination of user-friendly platforms and effective instructor-student interaction.

4.2 Summary on the Digital Technology Integration of Students

Table 2 presented the results of three indicators, namely attitude toward integrating, perceived usefulness, and perceived ease of use. It was found that students had a positive attitude toward integrating technology in their studies with a mean score of 4.26. They also perceived technology as useful with a mean score of 4.24. However, they found it less easy to use with a mean score of 4.14, which was the lowest among the three indicators. It is worth noting that all indicators received a similar descriptive equivalent of very high, indicating that students showed a high level of technology integration. Moreover, the overall standard deviation of 0.66 in the overall mean indicates that the variability of technology integration of students is close to the mean. Therefore, this shows the uniformity of the responses of students in this variable.

Table 2

Summary on the Digital Technology Integration of Students

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Perceived Ease of Use	.70	4.14	High
2. Perceived Usefulness	.63	4.24	Very High
3. Attitude Toward Integrating	.66	4.26	Very High
Overall	.66	4.21	Very High

The present study revealed that students strongly believe in the ease of use, usefulness, and attitude towards integrating technology in their learning environment. This result is consistent with the literature on the impact of technology on students' learning experiences. For instance, Ikhsan et al. (2019) emphasized the influence of technology on students' learning experiences. Additionally, Al-Azawei et al. (2018) showed that digital technology integration can improve learning outcomes and engagement among students. Bolliger and Halupa (2018) found that digital technology can enhance students' access to course materials and improve their academic

performance. Moreover, Sánchez et al. (2018) highlighted the importance of incorporating digital technology into the curriculum to prepare students for future careers and enhance their digital literacy skills. Therefore, the findings of the present study and previous research underscore the importance of integrating digital technology into education to enhance students' learning outcomes and prepare them for the increasingly digital world. It is crucial for educators and policymakers to recognize the benefits of technology integration and strive to incorporate it effectively into their teaching practices.

4.3 Summary on the Level of Students engagement

Table 3 shows students demonstrate a very high level of engagement in all three indicators, with affective engagement being the highest at a mean of 4.40, followed by behavioral engagement at 4.26, and cognitive engagement with the lowest mean of 4.34. This suggests that students are emotionally invested and actively participating in their learning, but may benefit from further development in critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Overall, these findings highlight the importance of fostering a supportive and engaging learning environment to enhance students' academic success.

Table 3

Summary on the level of Students engagement

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Affective Engagement	.64	4.40	Very High
2. Behavioral Engagement	.72	4.26	Very High
3. Cognitive Engagement	.62	4.34	Very High
Overall	.66	4.33	Very High

The research clearly indicates that students demonstrate a high level of engagement across all dimensions of learning: affective, behavioral, and cognitive. Affective engagement refers to students' emotional responses to learning, while behavioral engagement reflects their participation in school-related activities. Moreover, cognitive engagement demonstrates intrinsic motivation and investment in the learning process, as well as the ability to take ownership of it. Blended learning with interactive environments is a successful teaching strategy that has been shown to capture students' attention in classroom-based studies (Gil-Doménech & Berbegal-Mirabent, 2019).

In addition, the positive association between classroom emotional climate and grades is mediated by students' engagement, highlighting the importance of emotional classroom interactions in fostering academic success and increasing student engagement (Gutman & Schoon, 2018). These findings emphasize the need to cultivate positive classroom environments that foster emotional connections and encourage student engagement, regardless of grade level or gender.

4.4 Significance of the Relationship Between the Variables

Table 4 displays the significant relationship between the e-learning educational atmosphere and students' engagement, as well as technology integration and students' engagement.

The correlation analysis shows a strong positive correlation between the two variables, with a coefficient determination of 0.762 and a p-value less than 0.05, indicating that the relationship is statistically significant. These findings support Flavell's metacognitive theory, which suggests that adaptive course content can affect students' engagement levels by gathering and storing data on their confidence, accuracy, and knowledge. Additionally, Kuo et al. highlight the personalized and dynamic learning environment that e-learning provides in higher education, which can increase student engagement. The e-learning environment's interactive and dynamic nature, coupled with well-designed multimedia resources and interactive activities, can significantly enhance student engagement and promote active learning (Mwandosya et al., 2018). Learner control, interactivity, and timely feedback are essential components that shape the engagement levels of students in the e-learning context. When students have a sense of control over their learning and receive personalized feedback, they are more likely to remain engaged and motivated to learn (Ma & Yuen, 2011).

Table 4
Significance of the Relationship Between the Variables

Variables Correlated	r	p-value	Decision on H₀	Decision on Relationship
E-learning Educational Atmosphere & Student Engagement	0.762	0.000	Reject	Significant
Technology Integration & Student Engagement	0.743	0.000	Reject	Significant

The results of the study indicate a significant correlation between technology integration and student engagement in agribusiness programs. The strong positive correlation between these variables suggests that technology plays a vital role in enhancing students' engagement in learning. This finding is consistent with the literature, which emphasizes the importance of technology integration in higher education to improve student engagement and academic outcomes. For instance, Bond et al. (2020) highlight that technology integration can improve student engagement by facilitating interactive activities, contextualized lessons, and meaningful assessments. Similarly, Loannou et al. (2019) argue that technology integration can increase student engagement by providing teachers with effective resources for instruction, such as interactive communication and peer collaboration. Studies by Zhu and Chen (2020), Kwon and Lim (2018), and Kay and Greenhill (2016) also support the idea that technology integration can enhance student

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The chapter presented the summary of the significant findings of the study, the conclusions, and recommendations for possible implementations.

5.1 Summary of Findings

The significant findings of the study were the following:

1. For the level of e-learning educational atmosphere of students, awareness of the rules got the highest mean of 4.50 with a descriptive equivalent of very high and an SD of 0.59. It was followed by teaching quality with a mean of 4.43, a descriptive equivalent of very high, and an SD of 0.64. Next to teaching quality was ethics and professionalism with a mean of 4.43 and an SD of 0.62. It was followed by learner support with a mean of 4.31, a descriptive equivalent of very high, and an SD of 0.67. It was followed by programme effectiveness with a mean of 4.30, a descriptive equivalent of very high. On the other hand, Safety and Convenience got the lowest mean of 4.12 and an SD of 0.74. Additionally, programme effectiveness, teaching quality, ethics and professionalism, learner support, safety and convenience, and also awareness of the rules got a descriptive equivalent of very high. Furthermore, it had an overall mean of 4.35, an SD of 0.66, with a descriptive equivalent of high.

2. For the level of technology integration, attitude toward integrating got the highest mean of 4.26 and an SD of 0.66. This was followed by perceived usefulness with a mean of 4.24 and an SD of 0.63. On the other hand, perceived ease of use got the lowest mean of 4.14 and an SD of 0.70. Additionally, all indicators got a similar descriptive equivalent of very high. Furthermore, it had an overall mean of 4.21, an SD of 0.66, with a descriptive equivalent of very high.

3. For the level of student engagement, cognitive engagement got the highest mean of 4.34 and an SD of 0.62. This was followed by behavioral engagement with a mean of 4.26 and an SD of 0.72. On the other hand, affective engagement got a mean of 4.40 and an SD of 0.64. Additionally, all indicators got a similar descriptive equivalent of high. Furthermore, it had an overall mean of 4.33, an SD of 0.66, with a descriptive equivalent of high.

4. E-learning educational atmosphere had a significant relationship with students' engagement ($r=0.762$, $p=0.000$). In particular, the degree of correlation of the two variables had a very high positive correlation, and the p-value of the two variables was less than the 0.05 level of significance, which made them significant. This indicated a significant relationship between the e-learning educational atmosphere and student engagement. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. On the other hand, technology integration and student engagement ($r=0.743$, $p=0.000$). In particular, the degree of correlation of the two variables had a very high positive correlation, and the p-value of the two variables was less than the 0.05 level of significance, which made them significant. This indicated a significant relationship between technology integration and student engagement. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. 5. E-learning educational atmosphere had a significant influence on students' engagement ($\beta = 0.511$, $p < 0.000$). On the other hand, the

result revealed that technology integration had a significant influence on student engagement ($\beta = 0.356, p < 0$).

4. The study found that e-learning educational atmosphere had a significant influence on students' engagement ($\beta = 0.511, p < 0.000$). Additionally, the results revealed that technology integration had a significant influence on student engagement ($\beta = 0.356, p < 0.000$). Based on the level of significance, the first null hypothesis was rejected while the second hypothesis was also rejected.

5.2 Conclusions

Conclusions drawn from the study were as follows:

1. E-learning educational atmosphere of the school was much observed.
2. Technology integration of students was much evident.
3. Student engagement was much manifested.
4. There was a significant relationship between the e-learning educational atmosphere and student engagement. On the other hand, technology integration had a significant relationship with student engagement.
5. E-learning educational atmosphere had a significant influence on student engagement. On the other hand, technology integration significantly influenced student engagement.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings, analysis, and conclusion drawn in this study, the following recommendations were summarized:

1. Students, instructors, and school administrators were encouraged to value the importance of an e-learning educational atmosphere, technology integration, and Student engagement. Understanding the level of these areas may help to strengthen the effectiveness of learning.
2. Teachers, School administrators, and Local Colleges officials had to establish programs that enhanced students' Perceived Ease of Use in using technology in a classroom environment. This would help students to easily learn by integrating digital technologies. On the other hand, students' Safety and Convenience had to be improved when engaging in an e-learning atmosphere. This would help to make an electronic learning environment satisfying. Student's behavioral involvement had also to be raised because they would volunteer for and assist with school events like parent day and sports day.
3. The entire study emphasized the significant relationship and influence of e-learning educational atmosphere and technology integration on student engagement. With this, there was a decisive necessity to develop a more comprehensive curriculum to cater to the needs of the students in terms of agribusiness courses that concerned technology integration and an e-learning educational atmosphere as part of their learning experience. Bsab Instructors and administrators had to aim for a collaborative academic endeavor that would develop students' learning experience when using technology in learning.

4. Future researchers had to conduct further research focusing on students' safety convenience, perceived ease of use, and behavioral engagement in learning agribusiness courses.

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